

A methodological approach to aggregate multiple measures of hospital quality using variance-based weights

Authors: Meggiolaro A., Blankart R., Staudgart T., Schreyögg J.

ABSTRACT

Objective: This study presents an econometric approach to measure hospital performance and potentially compare quality of care between different health care systems. The method is based on the simultaneous estimation of accelerated failure time (AFT) models across four cardiovascular interventions and two outcomes. The two-stage variance-based weights approach has several advantages: first, the extent to which an indicator contributes to the aggregate index depends on the amount of its variance, second the risk adjustment reduces a potential hospital selection bias. The method was restricted to acute cardiovascular events occurred in Germany from 2005 to 2016.

Methods: Data were extracted from a large German sickness fund and further information on hospitals were obtained from Inkar databases. The two-stage regression approach estimated hospital performance over four specific indicators: ST elevation (STEMI), non-ST elevation (NSTEMI) acute myocardial infarction (AMI), Coronary Bypass Surgery (CABG or bypass) and Cardiac Resynchronization (ICD/CRT or HZM). Mortality and hospital readmissions were used as outcomes and severity of readmission was weighted for the length of hospital stay. The hospital estimates obtained in the first stage were aggregated in the second-stage. The AFT models were fitted by maximum likelihood (Newton Raphson algorithm). Results were normalized into an index range from zero to one. The sensitivity analysis tested the internal validity simulating several scenarios.

Results: Overall, 175,574 episodes that fulfilled the defined inclusion criteria occurred in 452 hospitals. We categorized 23,735 CABG; 55,415 ICD/CRT; 37,007 STEMI and 59,417 as NSTEMI. 10,876 patients died, and 157,046 were readmitted within one year. There were 164,698 right-censored observations related to death and 74,787 right-censored observations related to readmissions. The precision-based weights were higher for mortality than readmissions. In general, teaching hospitals performed better than non-teaching affiliates; in terms of ownership, private no profit hospitals exhibited a higher rank with respect to public and private groups.

Discussion: Overall, the AFT model resulted more efficient and informative compared with GLM models that rely on dichotomized data; additionally, the simultaneous estimation allows for correlation between different outcomes. Although the method could still raise issues pertaining to unobserved effects and endogeneity, we considered the method robust and *'fairly rich'* in front of a residual variability that we classified as stochastic. The index can be extended to further clinical areas and adapted to different healthcare systems.